

A novel synthesis pathway for oxide dispersion strengthened Fe–Cr alloys enabled by ultrasonic atomization

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Supplementary Material

Figure S1: SEM-BSE-micrographs of the ODS-Fe₂Y processing route: a) Microstructure of Fe₂Y master alloy along with the average elemental concentration in at.% in an inset, b) microstructure of the cast rods taken from top and bottom of one of the 4 rods used for UA, c) top view SEM image of powder produced by UA, and d,e) cross-section view of a powder particle showing fine particles dispersed uniformly in the matrix.

Figure S2: Schematic diagram of the ultrasonic atomization process.

Figure S3: XRD patterns of: a) as-cast, b) AA , c) HT and d) FAST. All XRD patterns confirm the presence of A2 phase (W prototype, space group 229) in the material across the entire processing route. No second phases were detected from the XRD patterns.

Table S1: List of all successful APT measurements on the AA and HT condition of the sample along with the Y distribution bulk composition (at. %) in these tips. AA1-7 represent the APT tips from the AA condition. HT1-2 represent the APT tips from the HT condition.

AA-1 No Precipitate						
Elements	Fe	Cr	Y	Ti	O	N
Bulk Composition	84.93	14.11	0.001	0.31	0.011	0.001
AA-2 No Precipitate						
Bulk Composition	81.67	13.37	0.001	0.44	0.024	0.002
AA-3 No Precipitate						
Bulk Composition	82.43	13.41	0.005	0.37	0.024	0.001
AA-4 No Precipitate						
Bulk Composition	84.27	13.09	0.001	1.22	0.007	0.01
AA-5 (Fig. 3a – main manuscript)						
Bulk Composition	85.68	12.02	0.77	0.98	0.04	0.21
AA-6 (Fig. 3a – main manuscript)						
Bulk Composition	84.22	11.79	1.66	1.24	0.007	0.01
HT-1 (Fig. 3b – main manuscript)						
Elements	Fe	Cr	Y	Ti	O	N
Bulk Composition	85.46	13.85	0.01	0.29	0.01	0.003
HT-2 (Fig. 3b – main manuscript)						
Bulk Composition	84.70	13.73	0.165	0.28	0.31	0.002

Figure S4: SEM-BSE micrograph of the left-over material in the ATO.

Table S2: Chemical composition of the leftover material in wt. %.

Elements	wt. %
Fe	82.9 ± 0.3
Cr	14.4 ± 0.1
Ti	0.4 ± 0.1
Y	2.3 ± 1.7

Figure S5: (a) Bright-field TEM image of the AA powder sample showing fine precipitates highlighted in yellow. The region selected for further analysis is indicated by a yellow circle. (b) Selected area electron diffraction (TEM-SAED) pattern acquired from the circled region in (a).

Table S3: Chemical composition of the dispersoid marked with yellow circle in Figure S4 measured by STEM-EDS.

Elements	Dispersoid (at. %)	Matrix (at. %)
Fe	72.9 ± 1.6	83.1 ± 0.6
Cr	6.6 ± 0.4	11.5 ± 0.3
Ti	0.5 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1
Y	16.6 ± 1.7	1.2 ± 0.4
O	3.3 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.4